

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: Quantification of inflammatory proteins in meconium/stool using UHPLC/MS

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Summary

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and food allergies are a highly prevalent and diverse group of intestinal disorders, potentially resulting in chronic inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract (e.g., Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis, and celiac diseases). Determination of fecal inflammatory proteins (calprotectin, myeloperoxidase, eosinophil-derived neurotoxin, eosinophil cationic protein, alpha-1-antitrypsin 1) and adaptive immunity effectors in meconium/stool allow to study intestinal development or identify and characterize type of inflammation in intestinal tract.

Table with analyzed proteins and the targeted peptides

Protein Number	Gene Name	Name	Abbreviation	Proteotypic Sequence
P01009-1	SERPINA1	Alpha-1-antitrypsin isoform 1	A1AT-1	AVLTIDEK
P01876	IGHA1	Immunoglobulin heavy constant alpha 1	IGHA1	TPLTATLSK
P01876+P01877	IGHA1+2	Immunoglobulin heavy constant alpha 1 and 2	IGHA1+2	SAVQGPPER
P01877	IGHA2	Immunoglobulin heavy constant alpha 2	IGHA2	DASGATFTWTPSSGK
P12724	RNASE3	Eosinophil cationic protein	ECP	NQNTFLR
P10153	RNASE2	Eosinophil-derived neurotoxin	EDN	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR
P05164	MPO	Myeloperoxidase	MPO	VVLEGGIDPILR
P05109	S100-A8	Calprotectin 1	CAL1	ALNSIIDVYHK
P06702	S100-A9	Calprotectin 2	CAL2	DLQNFLK
				LGHPDTLNQGEFK

Safety information

- Meconium/stool samples are classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.
- Isopropanol: flammable liquids, eye irritation, specific target organ toxicity following single exposure

Overview of reagents

- ammonium bicarbonate buffer (ABB), sodium deoxycholate (SDC), isopropanol (IPA) LC-MS grade, dithiothreitol (DTT), iodoacetamide (IAA), acetic acid, acetonitrile (ACN) LC-MS grade, formic acid (FA) LC-MS grade

Equipment

- 10 µL multichannel, 100 µL multichannel pipettes & 1000 µL automatic pipette
- Orbital shaker incubator
- Dry block heater for 96-well plates
- SpeedVac
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates
- pH meter
- 96-well plates SPE manifold with pump

Consumables & glassware

- 50 mL Falcon screw cap plastic vials
- 700 µL and 1500 µL 96-well plates with silicone sealing
- 150 µL 96-well PCR plates with silicone sealing
- 10 µL, 250 µL & 1 mL tips
- 500 µL and 1500 µL Eppendorf tubes
- 96 well plate SPE HLB PRIME 30 mg
- parafilm

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

Protein extraction buffer

- Meconium/stool sample are stored in -80°C freezer and thawed at room temperature
- 50 mM ABB (40 mg/10 mL in milliQ) with 5 g/L SDC
- For 40 mL of solution, weigh 160 mg ABB and 200 mg SDC into 50 mL screw plastic vial
- Add 40 mL of milliQ
- Solution should have pH=7.8 (measure with pH meter)

Solution can be kept for up to 7 days at 4 °C

Metabolite extraction solvent

- 80 % IPA

Reduction and alkylation solutions

- For preparation of 200 mM DTT dissolve 30.8 mg in 1 mL of milliQ water
- For preparation of 400 mM IAA dissolve 74 mg in 1 mL of milliQ water

Trypsin solution

- As described in trypsin standard manual, dissolve 100 µg lyophilized trypsin in 100 µL of 50 mM acetic acid.

SPE solutions

- 2 % FA, (pH<3)
- 50 % ACN with 2 % FA, (pH<3)
- 5 % ACN with 0.1 % FA

Reagents for mobile phase preparation

- ACN, LC-MS grade
- FA, LC-MS grade
- milliQ water

Standard preparation

- to prepare 1 mL of Peptide standard mixture mix volumes of 10 µM peptide standard listed in Table 1 and 350 µL of 5% ACN.

Table 1: Standard peptide mix volumes and concentrations

Protein	Internal Standard Peptide Sequence	Volume of 10 μ M standard [μ l]	Concentration of peptide in mixture [nM]	Concentration of standard in 50 μ l of sample
A1AT-1	AVLTIDEK	50	500	100
IGHA1	TPLTATLSK	50	500	100
IGHA1+2	SAVQGPPER	50	500	100
IGHA2	DASGATFTWTPSSGK	50	500	100
ECP	NQNTFLR	50	500	100
EDN	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR	50	500	100
MPO	VVLEGGIDPILR	50	500	100
CAL1	ALNSIIDVYHK	50	500	100
CAL2	DLQNFLK	50	500	100
	LGHPDTLNQGEFK	50	500	100

Sample preparation

Protein extraction

1. Stool/meconium samples are collected using swabs and stored in 2 mL vials at -80°C
2. Take samples out from freezer and leave thaw at room temperature for 20 *min*
3. Add 1 mL of 80 % IPA and shake 1600 RPM for 5 min
4. Spin down for 2 min at $12\,000 \times g$ and remove 50 μL of supernatant (for metabolomics analysis) into a new 500 μL vial
5. The rest of supernatant with swab let dry using speedvac overnight
6. Add 1500 μL of protein extraction buffer and homogenize using homogenizer with speed 4500 RPM, 2 pulses \times 20 s; inter-time 10 s
7. Spin down at $12\,000 \times g$ for 10min
8. Take out 400 μL of supernatant into a new vial
 - Take 10 μL of extract for total protein analysis using BCA kit (extract needs to be diluted 100x before BCA kit analysis)
9. Take 50 μL of supernatant for target protein analysis and place into a new 500 μL vial or 60 μL of supernatant into a 96-well PCR microplate (PCR microplate fits to heat block)

Reduction and alkylation

10. Add 5 μL (vial) or 6 μL (microplate) DTT solution and incubate at 90 °C for 10 min in heated block
11. Leave to cool down
12. Add 5 μL (vial) or 6 μL (microplate) IAA solution and incubate in dark for 30 min at room temperature

Trypsin digestion

(Take a 50 μL of sample from 96-well microplate and place into a new deep 96-well plate)

13. Add 10 μL standard peptide mixture and then 3 μL of trypsin solution (1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)
14. Close vials properly and seal with parafilm or seal microplate with silicone seal
15. Place into a heat shaker and shake at 200 RPM for 5 hours at 37 °C
16. Spin down for 30 s for 3000 x g
17. Stop digestion adding 200 μL of 2% FA

SPE in 96-well microplate format

18. Load samples into a SPE well plate and turn vacuum on to elute solution into a waste
19. Wash sample with 300 μL of 2% FA
20. Elute peptides with 200 μL 50 % ACN with 2 % FA into a 700 μL 96 well plate with V bottom
21. Dry out samples in speedvac at 40 °C for 3h
22. Store in freezer at -20 °C or dissolve in 50 μL 5 % ACN s 0.1 % FA before analysis

Mobile phase preparation

- Mobile phase A: 0.1 % FA in milliQ water
- Mobile phase B: 95 % ACN with 0.1 % FA

LC-QQQ analysis

23. Clean the source and nebulizer before measurement
24. Check solvent for needle rinsing
25. Check solvent for seals rinsing

26. Prepare mobile phase
27. Input sequence
28. Start LC-QQQ analysis run
29. Check initial blanks and QC

NOTE: If problems, stop run, cap or seal samples and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.

NOTE: Measure with every sample set:

- Instrument blank (Mobile phase A)
- QC (standard peptide mix)
- Calibration curve in matrix: prepare pool of meconium/stool extracts → spike Labeled standard mix (use 6 different concentration) → measure 6 calibration points with 3 - 6 replicates (6 replicates for LOD, LOQ determination)

LC-QQQ sequence setup

1. Clean_blank
2. Clean_blank
3. QC
4. Samples 1-3
5. Instrument blank
6. Sample 4-6
7. Instrument blank
8. Sample 7-9 ...

NOTE: measure Instrument blank after every 3 samples

NOTE: measure QC with every 30 samples

9. Calibration
10. End with Instrument blank, QC and 2 x Clean blank
11. Run samples with dSRM assay as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. SRM assay library for positive ion detection mode

Protein Number	Peptide Sequence	Precursor Ion	Product Ion	Qualified/ Quantified ion
P01009	AVLTIDEK.light	444.8	718.4	y6
P01009	AVLTIDEK.light	444.8	605.3	y5
P01009	AVLTIDEK.light	444.8	504.3	y4
P01009	AVLTIDEK.heavy	448.8	726.4	y6
P01009	AVLTIDEK.heavy	448.8	613.3	y5
P01010	AVLTIDEK.heavy	448.8	512.3	y4
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.3	741.5	y7
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.3	527.3	y5
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.3	419.8	y8
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.3	312.2	b3
P01876	TPLTATLSK.heavy	470.3	242.2	y2
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.3	733.4	y7
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.3	519.3	y5
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.3	415.8	y8
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.3	312.2	b3
P01876	TPLTATLSK.light	466.3	234.1	y2
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.light	756.9	1111.5	y10
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.light	756.9	1010.5	y9
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.light	756.9	863.4	y8
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.light	756.9	762.4	y7
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.light	756.9	475.3	y5
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.heavy	760.9	1119.6	y10
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.heavy	760.9	1018.5	y9
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.heavy	760.9	871.4	y8
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.heavy	760.9	770.4	y7
P01877	DASGATFTWTPSSGK.heavy	760.9	483.3	y5
P01877	SAVQGPPER.light	470.7	782.4	y7
P01877	SAVQGPPER.light	470.7	683.3	y6
P01877	SAVQGPPER.light	470.7	555.3	y5
P01877	SAVQGPPER.light	470.7	498.3	y4
P01877	SAVQGPPER.light	470.7	401.2	y3
P01877	SAVQGPPER.light	470.7	258.1	b3
P01877	SAVQGPPER.heavy	475.8	792.4	y7
P01877	SAVQGPPER.heavy	475.8	693.4	y6
P01877	SAVQGPPER.heavy	475.8	565.3	y5
P01877	SAVQGPPER.heavy	475.8	508.3	y4
P01877	SAVQGPPER.heavy	475.8	411.2	y3
P01877	SAVQGPPER.heavy	475.8	258.1	b3
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.light	636.9	887.5	y7
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.light	636.9	774.4	y6
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.light	636.9	661.3	y5
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.light	636.9	284.2	y2

P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.light	636.9	299.2	b3
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.heavy	640.9	895.5	y7
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.heavy	640.9	782.4	y6
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.heavy	640.9	669.3	y5
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.heavy	640.9	292.2	y2
P05109	ALNSIIDVYHK.heavy	640.9	299.2	b3
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.light	640.9	840.5	y8
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.light	640.9	498.3	y4
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.light	640.9	312.2	b3
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.heavy	645.9	850.5	y8
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.heavy	645.9	508.3	y4
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.heavy	645.9	312.2	b3
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.light	427.6	498.3	y4
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.light	427.6	249.7	y4
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.heavy	430.9	508.3	y4
P05164	VVLEGGIDPILR.heavy	430.9	254.7	y4
P06702	DLQNFLK.light	439.2	649.4	y5
P06702	DLQNFLK.light	439.2	521.3	y4
P06702	DLQNFLK.light	439.2	407.3	y3
P06702	DLQNFLK.light	439.2	260.2	y2
P06702	DLQNFLK.light	439.2	229.1	b2
P06702	DLQNFLK.heavy	443.2	657.4	y5
P06702	DLQNFLK.heavy	443.2	529.3	y4
P06702	DLQNFLK.heavy	443.2	415.3	y3
P06702	DLQNFLK.heavy	443.2	268.2	y2
P06702	DLQNFLK.heavy	443.2	229.1	b2
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.light	485.9	722.3	y6
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.light	485.9	608.3	y5
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.light	485.9	480.2	y4
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.light	485.9	294.2	y2
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.light	485.9	621.3	b6
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.heavy	488.6	730.4	y6
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.heavy	488.6	616.3	y5
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.heavy	488.6	488.3	y4
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.heavy	488.6	302.2	y2
P06702	LGHPDTLNQGEFK.heavy	488.6	621.3	b6
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.light	544.6	736.4	y6
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.light	544.6	710.4	y12
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.light	544.6	368.7	y6
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.light	544.6	473.9	y12
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.light	544.6	213.8	y5
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.heavy	548.0	746.4	y6
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.heavy	548.0	715.4	y12
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.heavy	548.0	373.7	y6
P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.heavy	548.0	477.3	y12

P10153	DPPQYPVVPVHLDR.heavy	548.0	217.1	y5
P12724	NQNTFLR.light	446.7	778.4	y6
P12724	NQNTFLR.light	446.7	650.4	y5
P12724	NQNTFLR.light	446.7	536.3	y4
P12724	NQNTFLR.light	446.7	435.3	y3
P12724	NQNTFLR.light	446.7	288.2	y2
P12724	NQNTFLR.heavy	451.7	788.4	y6
P12724	NQNTFLR.heavy	451.7	660.4	y5
P12724	NQNTFLR.heavy	451.7	546.3	y4
P12724	NQNTFLR.heavy	451.7	445.3	y3
P12724	NQNTFLR.heavy	451.7	298.2	y2

SRM metabolite quantitative/semiquantitative evaluation

Peptide concentrations are recalculated to protein concentration based on molecular weight. Concentrations are related to total protein concentration.

LC-QQQ method setup

Multisampler		
Injection volume	2.00 µL	
Needle Wash	Multi-wash	
Stoptime	As Pump/No Limit	
Posttime	Off	
Advanced		
Sampling Speed	Draw Speed	100 µL/min
	Eject Speed	100 µL/min
	Wait Time After Draw	0 s
Needle Height Position	Offset	-0.4 mm
	Use Vial/Well Bottom Sensing	Yes
High Throughput	Sample Flush-Out Factor	5
	Injection Valve to Bypass for Delay Volume Reduction	No
	Enable Overlapped Injection	No

Binary Pump				
Flow	0.300 mL/min			
Solvents	A	95%	0.1 % FA	
	B	5%	95 % ACN with 0.1 % FA	
Pressure Limits	Min	0 bar		
	Max	1200 bar		
Stoptime	35 min			
Posttime	30 s			
Advanced				
Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]	Flow [%]	Max. Pressure Limit [bar]
0	95	5	0.3	1200
25	30	70		
25.3	5	95		
30	5	95		
31	95	5		
35	95	5		

Column Comp.	
Advanced	
Column temperature	40 °C
Enable Analysis	When front door open
	When temperature is within ± 0.8 °C
Valve Position/Column After Run	Do not switch

QQQ		
Source		
Source parameters		
Gas Temp:	200 °C	
Gas Flow:	18 l/min	
Nebulizer:	25 psi	
Sheath Gas Temp:	350 °C	
Sheath Gas Flow:	12 l/min	
Capillary:	3500 V (Positive)	3000 V (Negative)
Nozzle Voltage:	500 V (Positive)	1500 V (Negative)
iFunnel parameters		
High Pressure RF	150 V (Positive)	90 V (Negative)
Low Pressure RF	60 V (Positive)	60 V (Negative)

Chromatogram					
Stop Time	No limit/As Pump				
Ion source	AJS ESI				
Time filtering	Peak width	0.05 min			
Time segments					
#	Start Time	Scan Type	Div Valve	Delta EMV (+)	Delta EMV (-)
1	0	dynamicMRM	To waste	0	0
2	2	dynamicMRM	To MS	0	0
3	25	dynamicMRM	To waste	0	0